

BIMdiff: Object-Level BIM Change Detection with Identifier Reconciliation

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Abstract

Today’s file-based Building Information Modeling (BIM) collaboration provides limited version comparison of design changes. Existing BIM change detection methods either assume identifier stability – and therefore fail when objects are deleted and recreated with new Globally Unique Identifiers (GUIDs) – or compute the changes at the level of IFC instances (e.g., #369=IFCLOCALPLACEMENT...) rather than building objects, such as walls and windows. We propose BIMdiff, an object-level change detection method to address these limitations. First, two geometry signature algorithms are proposed to detect geometry equivalence without relying on GUIDs, achieving 95.7% accuracy on constructed datasets. Second, we develop an end-to-end object-level change detection pipeline that combines GUID-based matching with a reconciliation module built on these geometry signatures. It reduces noise caused by unstable GUIDs and classifies object changes into six predefined statuses. Third, a tabular processing framework enables scalable computation on large models. On a 533K-object federated model, BIMdiff completes change detection in 24 seconds, while ifcdiff (part of IfcOpenShell) failed. Across the benchmark models, BIMdiff achieves up to 140 times faster processing and uses up to 17 times less memory than ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell). We illustrate two case studies by adopting BIMdiff for 1) tracking changes in multidisciplinary federated BIM projects, and 2) integrating change-highlighted reference models into authoring tools for assisting design. Additionally, we open source the tool IFC2StructuredData¹ that converts IFC files into structured tabular data for supporting BIMdiff and other applications.

Keywords: Version control, Change detection, Object differencing, Design collaboration, Geometry equivalence

1. Introduction

Building Information Modeling (BIM) has transformed the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry by enabling the creation of semantically rich digital representations of buildings [30, 3]. In practice, multidisciplinary teams collaborate asynchronously on federated models, exchanging design files through Common Data Environments (CDEs) following frameworks such as ISO 19650 [21]. This file-based workflow supports coordination across organizational boundaries but limits visibility into object-level changes. Change detection methods, meaning computing the delta between two versions of an artifact, are a well-established problem in other domains. For example, in software engineering, change detection between source code versions is commonly performed using diff algorithms [17, 24]. Version control systems such as Git [36] rely on these algorithms to identify added, deleted, or modified lines. In image processing, change detection algorithms compare pixel values or features to identify differences between images [29]. These techniques aim to identify meaningful changes while suppressing irrelevant differences between versions.

Applying change detection to BIM models presents unique challenges arising from their multi-dimensional nature. A BIM model covers building information across three distinct aspects: geometry, attributes, and

¹<https://github.com/ZijianWang-ZW/IFC2StructuredData>

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relationships. The Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) format serves as the predominant open standard for BIM data exchange. Among other options, it allows building information to be serialized in the STEP Physical File format (ISO 10303-21, also known as STEP Part 21) [20]. However, this serialization introduces challenges for computing the changes between two versions: a single building object may span hundreds of lines in an IFC file, and reordering or reformatting can produce spurious textual differences without semantic significance. For example, an object may be introduced by an IFC instance, such as #3554 = IFCWINDOW(. . .), while its geometry and attributes are defined in separate referenced instances elsewhere in the file. Unlike code, BIM data is not naturally line-based. For BIM, meaningful comparison should consider equivalence across all three aspects – geometry, attributes, and relationships – rather than line-based IFC instances alone.

Furthermore, BIM authoring tools often regenerate identifiers when objects are deleted and recreated, a common modeling operation that breaks identifier-based matching and inflates change reports with false additions and deletions. Most existing BIM differencing methods assume that identifiers remain stable across model versions and therefore rely on them to establish object correspondence. In practice, however, identifiers may be regenerated during delete-recreate, import-export, conversion, cross-tool exchange, and routine modeling operations, causing semantically unchanged objects to be misclassified as deletions and additions [7, 22].

Empirical studies have shown that GUID stability is weak in routine IFC workflows. For example, an analysis of 88 IFC files from 32 test cases found that on average only 1.3% of GUIDs were preserved through round-trip exchange, with the highest preservation rate reaching only 30.0%, even when no modification was made to the model [22]. Recent work further confirms that inconsistent IFC GUIDs can disrupt downstream cross-system data chains, indicating that identifier instability is a persistent interoperability issue rather than an edge case [12].

Researchers have explored multiple approaches to BIM change detection. Text-based methods apply line-level diff to IFC files but produce results that are difficult to interpret [28]. Content-based methods parse IFC schemas and match IFC instances hierarchically [31, 9], where the results are the similarity rates of two IFC files and cannot provide explicit building object changes (see Figure 1). Industry object-level comparison tools report object-level changes between versions [18, 15, 2], offering speed but remaining vulnerable when object identifiers are unstable. Graph-based methods represent models as property graphs and compute structural transformations [10, 11, 26], capturing relationship changes but introducing computational overhead and a lack of geometry consideration. Point-cloud methods leverage geometric registration for change identification [6], supporting multi-format input but requiring expensive spatial computation.

In this paper, we propose BIMdiff, an object-level change detection method. To address identifier instability, we introduce a reconciliation module that uses geometry and semantic equivalence to suppress the GUID instability noise. To support efficient processing at scale, we introduce a unified tabular representation for fast columnar computation. We further define a multi-dimensional change schema that decomposes object-level changes into geometry and attributes. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 presents the proposed method. Section 4 details the geometry signature algorithms for geometry equivalence detection. Section 5 describes the seven experiments conducted in this study and their results. Section 7 discusses the contributions, limitations, and future directions. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

This section reviews existing approaches to BIM change detection from both academic studies and industry tools, including plain text differencing, IFC content-based differencing, GUID-based object differencing, graph-based approaches, and point-cloud methods.

2.1. Plain Text Differencing

The simplest approach to BIM differencing treats model files as plain text and applies line-level diff algorithms. The IFC-SPF (STEP Physical File) format represents each entity instance on a single line,

63 making it amenable to text-based comparison [4]. Postle [28] developed ifc-git, a tool that integrates IFC
64 files with Git version control, enabling line-based change tracking using standard diff utilities.

65 Text-based differencing is fast and leverages mature tooling, but it has fundamental limitations for BIM
66 applications. Line-level changes do not correspond to semantic object changes: a single property modification
67 may affect multiple lines, while entity reordering may produce differences without semantic meaning. The
68 output, line additions and deletions, also requires expert interpretation to understand what changed in the
69 building model.

70 2.2. IFC Content-Based Differencing

71 Content-based methods address the limitations of text diff by parsing IFC files according to their schema
72 and performing structured comparison. An early contribution in this area is the work of Lee et al. [22],
73 who proposed a flattening-based approach to quantify similarities and differences between IFC files. The
74 flattening method replaces reference numbers in the STEP physical file with actual values through a recursive
75 strategy, decoding nested relationships to form unique description strings for each IFC instance. This
76 produces a representation where each line is self-contained, enabling comparison without dependence on
77 unstable reference numbers. The authors developed Compare P21, a software tool implementing their
78 proposed metrics: similarity rate, matching rate, GUID preservation rate, missing rate, and addition rate
79 Lee et al. [22]. This work represented an important early step toward quantitative IFC comparison beyond
80 visual inspection.

81 Building on content analysis principles, Sun et al. [33] developed IFCCompressor, a content-based com-
82 pression algorithm that identifies and eliminates redundant instances in IFC files. Although primarily a
83 compression tool, IFCCompressor’s underlying techniques for analyzing IFC tree structures and detecting
84 duplicate instances (particularly shared geometry among identical building elements) are directly relevant
85 to differencing approaches, as redundancy handling is a prerequisite for accurate comparison.

86 Shi et al. [31] proposed IFCdiff, a content-based automatic comparison approach that parses IFC instances
87 into hierarchical structures guided by the IFC schema, removes redundant and duplicate instances, and
88 performs an iterative bottom-up, level-by-level comparison from terminal nodes toward root entities to
89 identify matching versus non-matching instances. The method reports counts and ratios including total
90 instances, matching instances, similarity rate, and the numbers and rates of missing (deleted) and added
91 instances (See Figure 1). IFCdiff provides options to ignore GUID, owner history, or property-set order,
92 reducing irrelevant differences that would otherwise inflate change reports. However, IFCdiff’s comparison
93 scope is explicitly limited to the syntax-level content of IFC data instances extracted from the file. As
94 the authors state, the direct semantic content is not handled, and they position geometry comparison
95 and objectified relationships as part of a more complex semantic comparison problem left for future work.
96 Consequently, IFCdiff produces an IFC-instance diff rather than a BIM-level semantic diff.

97 Du & Duan [9] extended content-based comparison with IFC-SCC, a submodel comparison method
98 that extracts submodels as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) and generates signature strings for matching.
99 This approach reduces sensitivity to entity ordering and achieves faster comparison on large models by
100 focusing on submodel structures rather than individual instances. Content-based methods improve semantic
101 interpretability compared to text diff, but they remain confined to the IFC format and operate at the IFC
102 instance level rather than the building object level.

103 2.3. GUID-Based Object Differencing

104 The most widely deployed approach to BIM differencing relies on GUID matching. IFC entities represent-
105 ing building elements carry a GUID attribute intended to persist across versions. Entities with matching
106 GUIDs are compared for attribute and property changes, while unmatched GUIDs indicate additions or
107 deletions.

108 Open-source implementations include ifcdiff from IfcOpenShell [18], which matches IFC elements by
109 GUID and computes differences in attributes, geometry, and relationships, outputting results in JSON
110 format. To differentiate the two works with the same name, we use ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) to refer to this work
111 [18]. In the following part of this work, we only adopt this ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) for benchmark comparison

Figure 1: Screenshot of IFCdiff [31] which computes the metrics between two IFC STEP files, such as similarity of IFC instances rather than building objects.

112 due to the same concept of object-level differencing. Similarly, Speckle [32] uses its own identifier system to
 113 track objects across commits and highlight changes in a web-based viewer.

114 GUID-based methods are fast and produce object-level outputs that align with practitioner expecta-
 115 tions. However, they depend critically on identifier stability. In practice, GUIDs frequently change due
 116 to delete-recreate operations (deleting an object and recreating it with the same properties, which many
 117 authoring tools implement as distinct operations with new identifiers), re-export from different tools, or
 118 round-trip conversions [7]. When identifiers change, GUID-based methods report false additions and dele-
 119 tions, leading to large change lists that do not reflect the actual modifications in the model. This identifier
 120 instability problem is introduced in studies [12, 22] but not addressed in existing tools.

121 2.4. Graph-Based Approaches

122 Graph-based methods represent BIM models as graphs and leverage graph algorithms for differencing
 123 and version control. Esser et al. [10, 11] proposed a graph-based version control framework for asynchronous
 124 BIM collaboration. They parse file-serialized BIM models into a labeled property graph (LPG), where nodes
 125 represent schema-level instances (e.g., IFC entity instances) with attributes stored as node properties, and
 126 edges represent explicit schema associations and references between instances. Changes between versions
 127 are computed as graph edits and encoded as executable graph transformation patches (diff-and-patch). The
 128 latter work extends this mechanism to branch merging by applying patches through pattern matching and
 129 transformation rules to detect conflicts and enable controlled model integration [11].

130 However, the object-level granularity in this framework corresponds to schema instances rather than
 131 building objects, so a single building element update may decompose into many instance-level edits. Addi-
 132 tionally, during the representation of graphs, geometries are ignored due to the complexity. As a result, the
 133 computed diffs mainly capture changes in schema instances and their relationships, but not direct geometric
 134 modifications of building objects. This limits the completeness and interpretability of changes for BIM coordi-
 135 nation tasks, where geometry changes are often essential. Furthermore, because the output is expressed as
 136 IFC instance-level edits, additional analysis is required to reconstruct changes at the building-object level.

137 Oraskari & Törmä [26] proposed a Resource Description Framework (RDF) based method for computing
 138 differences between IFC model versions. The approach first converts IFC models into RDF graphs and ad-
 139 dresses the problem of unstable identifiers for anonymous entities (blank nodes). In the RDF representation,

140 IFC entities, attributes, and relationships are encoded as triples, and many elements become blank nodes
141 (e.g., entities without GUIDs, lists).

142 The core contribution is a set of signature algorithms that generate stable and deterministic identifiers
143 for blank nodes based on their local graph structure. This is achieved through incremental refinement and
144 a shortest-path-based signature method, effectively grounding the RDF graph. Once grounded, differences
145 can be computed as a simple triple-set comparison between two RDF graphs (added vs. removed triples).

146 However, the method operates at the RDF instance level. The output consists of added and removed
147 triples rather than object-level changes that explicitly separate attribute, geometry, and relationship mod-
148 ifications within a unified schema. The approach assumes stable GUIDs for IFC-rooted entities and does
149 not provide a GUID-insensitive reconciliation mechanism to eliminate delete-recreate noise caused by GUID
150 changes across exports.

151 *2.5. Point Cloud Approaches*

152 Geometry-based methods compare BIM models through their geometric representations, avoiding depen-
153 dence on identifiers or schema structures. Chuang & Yang [6] proposed the Change Component Identification
154 (CCI) framework to identify object-level changes between two time-variant datasets for facility management,
155 supporting both BIM-to-BIM and Scan-to-BIM comparison. The method represents each component as the
156 unit of change and determines its change state by combining semantic category constraints with spatial
157 screening and geometry-based similarity assessment. For BIM-to-BIM comparison, components are con-
158 verted into point clouds and compared using local geometric descriptors (Fast Point Feature Histograms,
159 FPFH) with registration methods including SAC-IA and ICP to decide whether a component is existing,
160 moved, newly added, missing, or uncertain. The framework outputs component change states together with
161 semantic labels and spatial locations, and reports accuracy evidence on BIM-to-BIM cases.

162 CCI supports multi-format input and avoids identifier dependence through its geometry-centric approach.
163 However, it is not designed as a collaboration-oriented change detection for asynchronous multidisciplinary
164 BIM collaboration; instead, it is primarily motivated by Scan-to-BIM and facility management update
165 scenarios. The point-cloud-centric pipeline introduces substantial computational overhead due to sampling
166 and registration, with the authors reporting approximately 7 hours of processing time for a building floor
167 with 60 million points. Moreover, its change representation is limited to a small set of geometry-driven
168 states and does not provide a multi-dimensional, object-level diff that decomposes changes into additional
169 modalities such as attribute and relationship deltas.

170 *2.6. Research Gaps and Objectives*

171 Table 1 summarizes the existing methods reviewed above, comparing their granularity, format support,
172 data structure, technical basis, and GUID dependency. Based on this analysis, we identify three research
173 gaps.

174 **Gap 1: Identifier instability.** Most practical tools rely on GUID matching, which fails under delete-
175 recreate scenarios common in BIM authoring workflows. Content-based methods, such as IFCdiff and
176 IFC-SCC, avoid GUID dependence but operate at IFC instance granularity (meaning the change of IFC
177 STEP files rather than BIM objects), while geometry-based methods, such as CCI, avoid identifiers entirely
178 but have high computational costs. A cost-aware method is missing for suppressing delete-recreate noise in
179 GUID-anchored object diffs and balancing robustness and computational efficiency.

180 **Gap 2: Lack of multi-dimensional object-level change schema.** Some approaches operate at the
181 IFC instance level, and their output requires substantial interpretation. A uniform schema for defining the
182 change status at the building object level by considering different dimensions of BIM data, such as geometry,
183 relationship, and attributes, is missing.

184 **Gap 3: Lack of performance benchmarking.** Tools that support change detection between BIM
185 models, such as ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell), are rarely described in sufficient detail to enable systematic compar-
186 ison. Therefore, performance comparisons across different model scales are lacking.

187 To address these gaps, this paper presents BIMdiff, an object-level change detection method for asyn-
188 chronous BIM collaboration. The objectives of this work are:

Table 1: Summary of existing BIM change detection methods.

Tool	Granularity	Source Format	Data Representation	Method	GUID Dependency
ifcgit [28]	IFC instance	IFC STEP	Pure text	Git line-based diff	No
Compare P21 [22]	IFC instance	IFC STEP	Flattened strings	Recursive flattening + metrics	No
IFCdiff (Shi et al. [31])	IFC instance	IFC STEP	Instance hierarchy	Bottom-up instance matching	No
IFC-SCC [9]	IFC instance	IFC STEP	DAG + signatures	Submodel signature matching	No
RDF signature [26]	IFC instance	IFC STEP	RDF triples	Graph signature algorithms	Yes
ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)[18]	Building object	IFC STEP	IFC model + JSON	GUID matching	Yes
Graph-based version control [10, 11]	Building object & IFC instance	IFC STEP	Property graph	Graph transformation rules	No
Speckle [32]	Building object	Multiple	Proprietary	GUID matching	Yes
CCI [6]	Building object	Multiple	Point clouds	FPFH registration + similarity	No
This study	Building object	Multiple	Tabular	GUID matching + Geometry-equivalence	No

- 189 1. To develop a GUID-insensitive reconciliation method that reduces identifier instability noise by lever-
190 aging geometry and semantic equivalence.
- 191 2. To partially tackle Gap 2 by defining and implementing a BIM object-level, multi-dimensional change
192 schema for geometry and attribute changes at the building object level, while leaving relationship
193 changes out of scope in this study.
- 194 3. To benchmark different data representations and diff methods across multiple model scales, demon-
195 strating the scalability advantages of a tabular diff pipeline.

196 To primarily reflect actual design changes, we adopt the following two experimental settings in this study.

197 (1) Same-tool version comparison. Each version pair compared in this study is exported from the same
198 authoring tool (e.g., Revit-vs-Revit or ArchiCAD-vs-ArchiCAD). This scope reflects current practice: a
199 single native discipline model is typically not editable across authoring tools.

200 (2) Consistent export configuration. The compared versions are exported using consistent settings, in-
201 cluding the same IFC schema version, unit conventions, and coordinate/export options, to reduce differences
202 introduced by exporter configuration rather than design changes.

203 3. BIMdiff Method

204 BIMdiff is an object-level change detection algorithm for BIM models. Figure 2 shows the overall
205 workflow, and Algorithm 1 formalizes the computation. BIMdiff takes two structured tables as input and
206 generates a unified diff table. Each row represents one building object from either BIM model version and
207 stores its properties, geometry, and change status label.

Figure 2: Overview of the BIMdiff pipeline. Steps 1–2 classify objects by GUID presence and merge both versions into a unified diff table T . Steps 3–4 compare properties and geometry. Step 5 assigns one of six change statuses. Step 6 reconciles false added/deleted pairs caused by GUID instability. The dashed box (right) expands the reconciliation module (Alg. 2), where two geometry signature algorithms – coordinate-sorted (Alg. 3) and geometric feature (Alg. 4) – are explored to compute geometry equivalence of object pairs.

Algorithm 1 Object-Level Change Computation

Require: V_{old} : previous version (tabular), V_{new} : current version (tabular)**Ensure:** Diff table T with status and property mask for each object

```
1: ▷ Step 1: Classify objects by GUID
2:  $G_{old} \leftarrow \text{GETGUIDS}(V_{old})$ 
3:  $G_{new} \leftarrow \text{GETGUIDS}(V_{new})$ 
4:  $S_{added} \leftarrow G_{new} \setminus G_{old}$ 
5:  $S_{deleted} \leftarrow G_{old} \setminus G_{new}$ 
6:  $S_{common} \leftarrow G_{old} \cap G_{new}$ 
7: ▷ Step 2: Merge tables on GUID
8:  $T \leftarrow \text{OUTERJOIN}(V_{new}, V_{old}, \text{key}=\text{GUID})$ 
9: ▷ Step 3: Compare attributes for common objects
10: for each property column  $p$  do
11:    $M[p] \leftarrow (T[p]_{new} \neq T[p]_{old})$ 
12: end for
13:  $\Delta_A \leftarrow \text{ANY}(M, \text{axis}=\text{columns})$ 
14: ▷ Step 4: Compare geometry signatures
15:  $\Delta_G \leftarrow (T[\text{geometry\_hash}]_{new} \neq T[\text{geometry\_hash}]_{old})$ 
16: ▷ Step 5: Assign initial status
17: for each row  $r$  in  $T$  do
18:    $r.\text{status} \leftarrow \text{ASSIGNSTATUS}(r, S_{added}, S_{deleted}, \Delta_A, \Delta_G)$ 
19: end for
20: ▷ Step 6: Reconcile GUID-reassigned objects
21:  $T \leftarrow \text{RECONCILE}(T)$  ▷ Algorithm 2
22: return  $T$ 
```

208 **3.1. Tabular Representation and Change Status**

209 BIMdiff uses an object-relational tabular representation of building models, for example, parsed from IFC
210 files or extracted through Revit Application Programming Interface (API). In this representation, each row
211 corresponds to one building object indexed by a GUID. The columns store object geometry and properties.
212 Geometry is stored in a dedicated column. Properties are represented as separate columns: each individual
213 property occupies one column and is stored as a string value, while each property set occupies one column
214 whose cell contains a dictionary of property–value pairs, as shown in Table 2. This tabular structure supports
215 efficient join, set, and vectorized comparison operations.

Table 2: Tabular schema for BIM object representation.

Column	Type	Description
GUID	string	Unique object identifier
Geometry	mesh	Mesh geometry represented by vertices and faces
Properties (multiple)	string/dict	Each individual property is stored in a separate column as a string, while each property set is stored in a separate column as a dictionary of property–value pairs.

216 BIMdiff detects multi-dimensional change. Instead of using a binary changed/unchanged result, it eval-
217 uates each object in terms of properties and geometry and assigns one of six statuses. Table 3 defines these
218 statuses.

Table 3: Object-level change status.

Status	Present in V_{old}	Present in V_{new}	Attribute delta	Geometry delta
Added	No	Yes	N.A.	N.A.
Deleted	Yes	No	N.A.	N.A.
Unchanged	Yes	Yes	No	No
Property Changed	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Geometry Changed	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Geometry & Property Changed	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: delta = change between versions; N.A. = not applicable.

3.2. Key Definitions

Before detailing each step, we define key terms used throughout this paper:

Delete–recreate action. A modeling operation in BIM authoring tools in which an object is deleted and then recreated. The recreated object may represent the same intended building object, but receives a new GUID.

Geometry equivalence. In this study, geometry is represented as meshes. Two objects are geometry equivalence if their mesh representations encode the same shape and spatial placement. This is used to determine whether an object’s geometry has changed between versions.

Geometry signature. A deterministic hash value computed from the geometric features of a mesh. It is used as a compact representation for geometry comparison across versions.

Reconciliation. A post-processing step that determines object correspondence when GUIDs change across versions. It is used to correct false added/deleted statuses caused by GUID instability.

3.3. Step 1-2: Object Alignment and Classification

This phase corresponds to Steps 1 and 2 of Algorithm 1. First, the algorithm extracts GUIDs from both versions. It then uses set operations to partition the union of objects ($V_{old} \cup V_{new}$). Based on the GUID presence, the objects are divided into three disjoint sets: added, deleted, and common.

After this classification, we construct the difference table (T) shown in Table 4 by performing an outer join on the GUID column. This operation merges attributes from the two versions into one row for each object. To avoid column name collisions, suffixes such as `_old` and `_new` are appended to the column names. During the outer join, added objects have null values in all `_old` columns, and deleted objects have null values in all `_new` columns.

After this classification, we construct the difference table (T) shown in Table 4 by performing an outer join on the GUID column. This operation merges attributes from the two versions into one row for each object. In particular, each row in T represents one object identified by its GUID, while the columns store different properties of that object (e.g., color and length) from the two versions. To avoid column name collisions, suffixes such as `_old` and `_new` are appended to the property names, so that each property is represented as an old–new column pair. The **Status** column indicates whether the object belongs to the common, added, or deleted set. During the outer join, added objects have null values in all `_old` columns, and deleted objects have null values in all `_new` columns.

As illustrated in Table 4, the columns `Color_old/Color_new` and `Length_old/Length_new` are examples of different object properties recorded before and after the change. This unified tabular structure supports the later comparison steps by converting object-by-object comparison into column-wise operations over the whole table.

Table 4: An illustrative example of the difference table (T) constructed via outer join.

GUID	Status	Color_old	Color_new	Length_old	Length_new	...
id_001	S_{common}	Red	Blue	10.5	10.5	...
id_002	S_{added}	NULL	Green	NULL	12.0	...
id_003	$S_{deleted}$	Black	NULL	15.0	NULL	...

3.4. Step 3-4: Multi-Dimensional Difference Detection

For the common objects (S_{common}), BIMdiff compares properties and geometry to detect changes. This step separates property changes from geometry changes.

The first aspect compares properties. BIMdiff performs column-wise vector comparison instead of row-by-row iteration. For each property column p , it compares $V_{old}[p]$ and $V_{new}[p]$ in a null-safe manner. Two values are treated as equal if they are identical or both null. All other cases, including a change between null and non-null, are treated as different. The property change indicator Δ_A is set to true if any property column differs.

The second aspect compares geometry. In the main BIMdiff pipeline, geometry comparison uses a coordinate-sorted geometry signature because of its runtime efficiency. This signature is a deterministic hash computed from canonicalized mesh geometry, and the geometry change indicator Δ_G is set to true when the signatures of the old and new versions differ. Section 4 presents the coordinate-sorted signature in detail and introduces a second geometric feature signature for comparison in the reconciliation context.

3.5. Step 5-6: Status Assignment and Reconciliation

After property and geometry comparison, BIMdiff assigns a change status to each object in the difference table T . The assignment is based on three signals: object existence, property differences (Δ_A), and geometry differences (Δ_G).

The algorithm first assigns initial statuses from object existence. If an object appears only in V_{new} , it is assigned the status Added. If it appears only in V_{old} , it is assigned the status Deleted. For objects in S_{common} , BIMdiff assigns the status from the combination of Δ_A and Δ_G , as defined in Table 3. If both indicators are false, the object is Unchanged. If only Δ_A is true, the object is Property Changed. If only Δ_G is true, the object is Geometry Changed. If both indicators are true, the object is Geometry & Property Changed.

This initial assignment is based on GUID alignment and therefore remains sensitive to GUID instability. A typical BIM authoring scenario is that a designer edits an element in a modeling tool by deleting and recreating it, or by performing an operation such as copy-replace, split-merge, or family/type substitution. Although the resulting element may remain identical in type, geometry, and properties, the authoring tool may assign it a new GUID during export. In a GUID-based comparison, this situation appears as a false Deleted/Added pair rather than as object continuity. As a result, the diff table overstates the number of changes and misrepresents the actual modeling operation.

To address this problem, BIMdiff applies a reconciliation step (Alg. 2) after the initial status assignment. This step re-establishes object correspondence for GUID-unstable cases using content signatures rather than identifiers alone. Each content signature combines object type, geometry signature, and serialized properties. Matching content signatures indicate content-identical objects with different GUIDs. BIMdiff then removes the false Deleted/Added pair and restores the corresponding object continuity in the diff table.

Algorithm 2 Reconciliation of GUID-Unstable Objects

Require: Diff table T with initial status from Algorithm 1**Ensure:** Updated T : content-identical Added/Deleted pairs reconciled

```
1:  $A \leftarrow \{r \in T \mid r.\text{status} = \text{Added}\}$ 
2:  $D \leftarrow \{r \in T \mid r.\text{status} = \text{Deleted}\}$ 
3: if  $A = \emptyset$  or  $D = \emptyset$  then
4:   return  $T$  ▷ nothing to reconcile
5: end if

6: ▷ Compute content signatures based on geometry signatures (hashes) (Sec. 4)
7: for each  $r \in A$  do
8:    $\sigma(r) \leftarrow \text{CONTENTHASH}(r.\text{type}_{new}, r.\text{geometry\_hash}_{new}, r[P]_{new})$ 
9: end for
10: for each  $r \in D$  do
11:    $\sigma(r) \leftarrow \text{CONTENTHASH}(r.\text{type}_{old}, r.\text{geometry\_hash}_{old}, r[P]_{old})$ 
12: end for

13: ▷ Pair-match by signature
14: for each  $s \in \sigma(A) \cap \sigma(D)$  do
15:    $A_s \leftarrow \{r \in A \mid \sigma(r) = s\}$ 
16:    $D_s \leftarrow \{r \in D \mid \sigma(r) = s\}$ 
17:    $n \leftarrow \min(|A_s|, |D_s|)$ 
18:   Mark  $n$  rows from  $A_s$  as unchanged ▷ keep new GUID
19:   Remove  $n$  rows from  $D_s$  out of  $T$  ▷ drop stale GUID
20: end for
21: return  $T$ 
```

287 The reconciliation step also depends on the design of the geometry signature. In the main pipeline,
288 BIMdiff uses the coordinate-sorted signature for efficiency. However, reconciliation is more sensitive to
289 serialization noise in geometry matching. We therefore further explore two geometry signature algorithms
290 by using coordinates and geometric features, respectively, in Section 4 and compare their performance for
291 reconciliation.

292 4. Geometry Signature Algorithms and Comparison

293 Step 4 and Step 6 of the BIMdiff pipeline (Figure 2) both rely on geometry comparison, but they operate
294 under different inputs and requirements.

295 In Step 4 of the main BIMdiff pipeline, geometry comparison is performed between objects that have
296 already been aligned by GUID. The goal is to determine whether the geometry of the aligned object has
297 changed between versions. In this setting, direct and exact comparison is sufficient, and a coordinate-sorted
298 signature (Sec. 4.1) computed directly from the mesh is adopted.

299 In Step 6, reconciliation compares candidate Added and Deleted objects to recover object correspon-
300 dence under GUID instability. This task is more sensitive to serialization noise and regeneration effects,
301 and therefore requires a more robust signature design. We therefore also introduce a geometric feature
302 signature (Sec. 4.2) for this purpose. The following subsections describe the two algorithms and compare
303 their robustness.

304 4.1. Coordinate-Sorted Signature

305 The coordinate-sorted signature computes a deterministic hash directly from mesh geometry by canoni-
306 calizing vertex order and face order before hashing. The method is invariant to vertex ordering, face ordering,
307 and face winding, and is suitable for comparing objects that have already been aligned by GUID. In this

308 subsection, V denotes world-space vertices obtained after applying the object’s stored transform to its local
 309 mesh vertices. Algorithm 3 presents the procedure.

Algorithm 3 Coordinate-Sorted Signature

Require: Vertices $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$, Faces $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$

Ensure: Signature string S

```

1:  $\mathbf{V} \leftarrow \text{array}(V)$ ;  $\mathbf{F} \leftarrow \text{array}(F)$ 
2:  $\mathbf{V}[\mathbf{V} = 0] \leftarrow +0.0$  ▷ Canonicalize signed zeros
3: ▷ Step 1: Sort vertices by coordinates
4:  $\pi \leftarrow \text{sort\_by\_coordinates}(\mathbf{V})$  ▷ Sort by  $x$ , then  $y$ , then  $z$ 
5:  $\mathbf{V}' \leftarrow \mathbf{V}[\pi]$ 
6: ▷ Step 2: Build inverse permutation and remap faces
7:  $\pi^{-1}[\pi] \leftarrow [0, 1, \dots, n - 1]$ 
8:  $\mathbf{F}' \leftarrow \pi^{-1}[\mathbf{F}]$ 
9: ▷ Step 3: Canonicalize winding and sort faces
10:  $\hat{\mathbf{F}} \leftarrow \text{sort}(\mathbf{F}', \text{axis} = 1)$  ▷ Sort indices within each triangle
11:  $\tilde{\mathbf{F}} \leftarrow \text{sort\_faces}(\hat{\mathbf{F}})$  ▷ Sort rows by index triplets
12: ▷ Step 4: Hash signature
13: return  $\text{SHA256}(\mathbf{V}'.\text{tobytes}() \parallel \tilde{\mathbf{F}}.\text{tobytes}())$ 

```

310 Before sorting, we map any -0.0 values in vertex coordinates to $+0.0$. This removes inconsistencies for
 311 numerically identical coordinates and avoids false signature differences caused by signed-zero representations
 312 in floating-point exports.

313 **Step 1: Sort vertices by coordinates.** All vertices are sorted lexicographically by their (x, y, z)
 314 coordinates to obtain a canonical vertex order. This removes dependence on the original vertex enumeration
 315 and produces the same vertex order for meshes with identical coordinates.

316 **Step 2: Remap faces using the inverse permutation.** After vertex reordering, face indices are
 317 remapped with the inverse permutation π^{-1} . This preserves the geometric meaning of each triangle under
 318 the new vertex order.

319 **Step 3: Canonicalize triangle winding and sort faces.** Each triangle is normalized by sorting its
 320 three vertex indices. This removes sensitivity to cyclic permutations and winding reversal. The face list is
 321 then sorted by index triplets to remove dependence on face ordering in the input mesh.

322 **Step 4: Compute the signature by hashing canonical arrays.** The signature is computed as
 323 the SHA256 hash of the concatenated byte streams of the canonicalized vertex array and face array. The
 324 resulting signature is deterministic and invariant to vertex ordering, face ordering, and face winding.

325 The method is intentionally sensitive to translation and rotation, because BIMdiff treats both shape
 326 and spatial placement as part of geometry change. However, it is also sensitive to small floating-point
 327 perturbations, which may change the signature even when the underlying geometry is practically unchanged.
 328 This limitation is less critical in Step 4, where geometry comparison is performed on objects that have already
 329 been aligned by GUID, but it becomes more important in reconciliation under GUID instability.

330 4.2. Geometric Feature Signature

331 The geometric feature signature is designed as a more robust alternative for geometry matching in recon-
 332 ciliation under GUID instability. Instead of hashing mesh coordinates directly, it hashes a set of geometric
 333 descriptors derived from the mesh. These descriptors include shape descriptors and pose descriptors. The
 334 shape descriptors improve robustness to vertex ordering, face ordering, and small numerical perturbations
 335 in exported meshes. The pose descriptors preserve sensitivity to translation and rotation, which BIMdiff
 336 treats as geometry changes. Table 5 summarizes the descriptors used in this signature.

337 In Algorithm 4, we first canonicalize signed zeros and quantize floating-point values to a fixed precision.
 338 This reduces false mismatches caused by small numerical perturbations in exported mesh coordinates. The

Table 5: Descriptors used in the geometric feature signature.

Feature	Category	Description
Edge length spectrum \mathcal{E}	Shape	Sorted list of unique mesh edge lengths; captures object proportions independent of ordering.
Face area spectrum \mathcal{A}	Shape	Sorted list of triangle areas; summarizes surface-scale distribution under re-export.
Vertex degree histogram \mathcal{H}	Shape	Histogram of vertex degrees induced by mesh edges; captures coarse connectivity/topology.
Total edge length L_{total}	Shape	Sum of all edge lengths; scalar summary of overall object scale.
Total surface area A_{total}	Shape	Sum of all face areas; scalar summary of overall surface extent.
Centroid c	Pose	Mean of vertex coordinates; detects object translation in the global frame.
Principal-axis frame U	Pose	PCA axes of centered vertices (canonicalized); detects object orientation in the global frame.

signature is then computed from five groups of descriptors: edge lengths, face areas, vertex degrees, centroid, and principal-axis frame.

Step 1: Compute the edge length spectrum. We extract the unique undirected edges induced by the triangle list and compute the Euclidean length of each edge. The resulting lengths are sorted to obtain an order-independent descriptor of object proportions.

Step 2: Compute the face area spectrum. We compute the area of each triangle and sort the resulting values. This descriptor summarizes the surface-scale distribution of the mesh and is invariant to rigid transformations.

Step 3: Compute the vertex degree histogram. We derive vertex degrees from the edge set and build a histogram over degree values. This captures coarse mesh connectivity and helps distinguish shapes with similar length or area distributions.

Step 4: Compute pose descriptors. We compute the centroid of the vertices to represent translation. We then compute a principal-axis frame by PCA on centered vertices and canonicalize the frame orientation to obtain a deterministic descriptor of object orientation.

Step 5: Hash all descriptors into a single signature. We compute the total edge length L_{total} and total surface area A_{total} as additional scalar summaries. All quantized descriptors are then concatenated and hashed into a single geometry signature S .

Algorithm 4 Geometric Feature Signature

Require: Vertices V , Faces F , precision p **Ensure:** Geometry signature S

```
1:  $\mathbf{V} \leftarrow \text{array}(V)$ ;  $\mathbf{F} \leftarrow \text{array}(F)$ 
2:  $\mathbf{V}[\mathbf{V} = 0] \leftarrow +0.0$  ▷ Canonicalize signed zeros
3: Define quantization  $Q(x) = \lfloor x \cdot 10^p + 0.5 \rfloor$ 
4: ▷ Step 1: Edge length spectrum
5:  $E \leftarrow \{(i, j) : \text{unique undirected edges induced by } \mathbf{F}\}$ 
6:  $\mathcal{E} \leftarrow \text{sort}(\|\mathbf{V}_i - \mathbf{V}_j\|_2 : (i, j) \in E)$ 
7: ▷ Step 2: Face area spectrum
8:  $\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \text{sort}(\frac{1}{2}\|(\mathbf{V}_b - \mathbf{V}_a) \times (\mathbf{V}_c - \mathbf{V}_a)\|_2 : (a, b, c) \in \mathbf{F})$ 
9: ▷ Step 3: Vertex degree histogram
10: Compute degrees  $d_v$  from  $E$  for all vertices  $v$ 
11:  $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \text{histogram}([d_v : v \in \mathbf{V}])$ 
12: ▷ Step 4: Pose descriptors (centroid + orientation)
13:  $c \leftarrow \frac{1}{|\mathbf{V}|} \sum_{v \in \mathbf{V}} v$ 
14:  $\tilde{\mathbf{V}} \leftarrow [v - c : v \in \mathbf{V}]$  ▷ Center vertices
15:  $\Sigma \leftarrow \frac{1}{|\mathbf{V}|} \sum_{v \in \tilde{\mathbf{V}}} v v^\top$  ▷  $3 \times 3$  covariance
16:  $U \leftarrow [u_1, u_2, u_3] \leftarrow \text{PCA\_axes}(\Sigma)$  ▷ Eigenvectors sorted by eigenvalues
17:  $U \leftarrow \text{canonicalize\_frame}(U, \tilde{\mathbf{V}})$  ▷ Fix sign and handedness
18: ▷ Step 5: Hash all descriptors into a single signature
19:  $A_{\text{total}} \leftarrow \sum \mathcal{A}$ ;  $L_{\text{total}} \leftarrow \sum \mathcal{E}$ 
20:  $S \leftarrow \text{SHA256}(Q(\mathcal{E}) \parallel Q(\mathcal{A}) \parallel \mathcal{H} \parallel Q(A_{\text{total}}) \parallel Q(L_{\text{total}}) \parallel Q(c) \parallel Q(U))$ 
21: return  $S$ 
```

4.3. Complexity and Comparison

The two methods are different in both concepts adopted and computational cost. The coordinate-sorted signature hashes canonicalized vertex coordinates and face indices directly. Its comparison is therefore exact at the mesh-array level, but it is sensitive to small floating-point perturbations. By contrast, the geometric feature signature hashes a descriptor vector composed of edge-length spectra, face-area spectra, connectivity statistics, and pose descriptors. This representation is less direct, but it is more robust to minor serialization differences caused by vertex or face reordering and small numerical perturbations.

Theoretical complexity also reflects this difference. For the coordinate-sorted signature, the runtime is dominated by sorting vertices and faces, giving $O(n \log n + m \log m)$ for a mesh with n vertices and m faces. For the geometric feature signature, computing descriptors requires edge extraction and degree computation in $O(|E|)$, face-area computation in $O(m)$, centroid and covariance accumulation in $O(n)$, and constant-time eigendecomposition on the resulting 3×3 covariance matrix. The runtime is then dominated by sorting the edge-length and face-area spectra, giving $O(|E| \log |E| + m \log m + n)$, where $|E|$ is the number of unique edges induced by the mesh. For triangle meshes, $|E| = O(m)$ in practice, so the total runtime can be written as $O(m \log m + n)$, but with higher constant factors than the coordinate-sorted signature.

The following section evaluates these two algorithms. The experiments first test their geometry-equivalence functionality on controlled cases, then examine the geometric feature signature through ablation studies, and finally compare the two methods under robustness scenarios. The study then returns to the full BIMdiff pipeline and evaluates end-to-end performance and efficiency in practical BIM differencing tasks.

5. Experiments

This section evaluates the proposed methods through seven experiments, summarized in Table 6. The experiments are organized into five categories. First, a functionality experiment evaluates geometry-equivalence detection on controlled edits (Sec. 5.3). Second, two ablation experiments analyze the geometric feature signature in terms of feature contribution and threshold selection (Sec. 5.4.1 and Sec. 5.4.2). Third, two

380 robustness experiments compare the coordinate-sorted and geometric feature signatures under IFC schema
 381 variation and tessellation noise (Sec. 5.5.1 and Sec. 5.5.2). Fourth, an end-to-end experiment evaluates two
 382 BIMdiff configurations on a version chain, one using the coordinate-sorted signature and the other using the
 383 geometric feature signature in reconciliation (Sec. 5.6). Finally, a benchmark experiment compares BIMdiff
 384 with ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) across model scales (Sec. 5.7). Three datasets were constructed to support these
 385 experiments (Sec. 5.2).

Table 6: Experiment summary.

Section	Objective	Target Algorithms	Dataset
Sec. 5.3	Functionality: Geometry-equivalence	Alg. 3, Alg. 4	A
Sec. 5.4.1	Ablation: feature contribution	Alg. 4	A
Sec. 5.4.2	Ablation: threshold selection	Alg. 4	A
Sec. 5.5.1	Robustness: IFC schema variation	Alg. 3, Alg. 4	A
Sec. 5.5.2	Robustness: tessellation noise	Alg. 3, Alg. 4	A
Sec. 5.6	BIMdiff end-to-end performance	BIMdiff + Coord-Sorted, BIMdiff + Feat ($\lambda=0.5$)	B
Sec. 5.7	Benchmark efficiency	BIMdiff, ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	C

386 We ran all experiments on a workstation with a 12th Gen Intel Core i7-12700H CPU and 32 GB RAM. For
 387 parsing information from IFC files and geometry tessellation to the required tabular format, we developed a
 388 tool, IFC2StructuredData (Appendix 8), using IfcOpenShell 0.8.4 [19]. For implementing BIMdiff and the
 389 geometry signature algorithms, we used pandas 2.3.3 [27] and numpy 2.2.6 [25] for tabular operations and
 390 trimesh 4.7.4 [8] for geometry processing.

391 5.1. Evaluation Metrics

392 We report binary classification metrics for geometry-equivalence detection in Section 5.3–5.5.2. The task
 393 takes a set of old–new object pairs with known correspondence and predicts whether each pair is geometry-
 394 equivalence. We treat geometry-equivalence as the positive class. For each evaluated pair, the prediction
 395 falls into one of four outcomes:

- 396 • **True positive (TP):** the pair is geometry-equivalence in the ground truth and the method predicts
 397 geometry-equivalence.
- 398 • **True negative (TN):** the pair is not geometry-equivalence in the ground truth and the method
 399 predicts not geometry-equivalence.
- 400 • **False positive (FP):** the pair is not geometry-equivalence in the ground truth but the method
 401 predicts geometry-equivalence.
- 402 • **False negative (FN):** the pair is geometry-equivalence in the ground truth but the method predicts
 403 not geometry-equivalence.

404 We compute precision, recall, and accuracy from these counts:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}. \quad (3)$$

Precision measures the reliability of positive predictions. It penalizes FP, declaring non-equivalent objects as equivalent. Recall measures coverage of the positive class. It penalizes FN, missing truly equivalent pairs. Accuracy measures overall correctness across both classes.

Additionally, in Section 5.6, we report an accuracy for BIM differencing. That accuracy is a multi-class object-status accuracy defined on the end-to-end label set and is not comparable to the binary geometry-equivalence accuracy defined above. For the benchmark, we report processing time, excluding parsing and file processing time, together with peak memory, as detailed in Section 5.7.

5.2. Datasets Overview

We used three datasets to evaluate different aspects of the method, as shown in Table 7. Dataset A is a controlled geometry-equivalence dataset used for functionality, ablation, and robustness experiments. Dataset B is a version chain used for end-to-end BIMdiff evaluation under controlled edits and GUID instability. Dataset C is a collection of industrial-scale version pairs used for the efficiency benchmark. Datasets B and C are introduced with their corresponding experiments for clarity.

Table 7: Overview of the three datasets.

Dataset	Content and purpose	Scale	Used in
A	Manually recorded ground truth for geometry equivalence (delete-recreate, unchanged/movement).	69 objects, 15 object types	Sec. 5.3–Sec. 5.5.2
B	A version chain with controlled edits for end-to-end BIMdiff testing.	4 versions in a chain	Sec. 5.6
C	Seven version pairs across disciplines for efficiency benchmark.	7 models with versions, 1K to 533K objects	Sec. 5.7

5.2.1. Dataset A: Geometry-equivalence Dataset

We constructed Dataset A using Autodesk Revit 2025 to evaluate geometry-equivalence detection under realistic modeling diversity. We manually edited the model and recorded ground truth labels for each test case. Dataset A contains 69 objects across 15 IFC classes and spans multiple disciplines and geometric complexities (Fig. 3).

We constructed this dataset by controlling several modeling factors to reflect realistic BIM editing behavior while maintaining experimental traceability. First, we ensured discipline coverage, such as architectural elements (e.g., walls, doors, windows), structural elements (e.g., columns, slabs), and MEP components (e.g., pipes, ducts, fittings). Second, we incorporated varying geometry complexity, ranging from simple solids to curved geometries that are sensitive to tessellation. Third, we controlled object granularity, including both standalone elements and complex assemblies (e.g., stairs and curtain walls).

In addition, the dataset includes hosted objects (e.g., windows in walls) and connected objects (e.g., pipe segments connected by fittings). For modeling changes, we created unchanged cases, delete-recreate cases with new GUIDs, and movement or modification cases, including micro-movements such as translating a door by 1 mm. These controlled scenarios allow us to isolate the effects of identifier instability and geometric sensibility, and to assess whether the algorithm detects true geometric equivalence rather than superficial modeling artifacts. In total, Dataset A includes 28 delete-recreate pairs and 41 unchanged/movement pairs.

5.2.2. IFC file processing

Models were exported from Revit 2025 as IFC files using the IFC 4.3 schema with other default settings, such as "Level of Detail" set to "Low", "Export IFC common property sets", and "Export base quantities".

We used the developed IFC2StructuredData (Appendix 8) to extract geometry and attributes from the IFC STEP Physical File into structured tabular outputs. For the BIMdiff algorithms, each object record contains the GUID, local mesh geometry, a separate transformation matrix, and properties as explained in Table 2. For geometry processing, IFC2StructuredData converts different IFC geometric representations

Figure 3: Dataset A with 69 objects across different types, disciplines, and scenarios.

442 into a unified mesh representation. Each IFC product is tessellated into mesh vertices and triangular faces
 443 through the `IfcOpenShell` geometry functions [19]. The mesh is stored in local object coordinates, while the
 444 transformation matrix preserves the object’s position and orientation in world space. All geometric values
 445 are normalized to meters.

446 5.3. Geometry-equivalence Functionality

447 We evaluate the geometry-equivalence functionality of the proposed Algorithm 3 (Coordinate-Sorted
 448 Signature) and Algorithm 4 (Geometric Feature Signature) on Dataset A. Table 8 reports the results.

Table 8: Functionality test results on Dataset A.

Algorithm	TP	TN	FP	FN	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Alg. 3 (Coord-Sorted)	57	9	0	3	95.7%	100.0%	95.0%
Alg. 4 (Feat)	57	9	0	3	95.7%	100.0%	95.0%

449 Both methods achieve 95.7% accuracy, 100% precision, and 95.0% recall. All three errors are false
 450 negatives from delete-recreate object pairs.

451 Since the two proposed algorithms are rule-based with explicit geometric features, we further investigated
 452 whether these false negatives could come from instability in the Revit IFC export process, i.e., whether
 453 identical geometries might be altered during export. To verify this, we exported the same model from Revit
 454 twice without any modifications and computed the diff between the two IFC files. The results showed that
 455 all objects remained identical, with no detected differences. This confirms that the Revit IFC exporter is
 456 deterministic when no model changes are made.

457 After further investigation, all three false negatives originate from a single `IfcStair` assembly that
 458 was deleted and recreated. This assembly contains 11 subcomponents: 8 `IfcMember`, 2 `IfcRailing`, and

459 1 IfcStairFlight. The algorithms correctly match the 8 IfcMember but fail on the remaining 3 objects.
 460 Fig. 4 visualizes the mesh-level differences for one of the two IfcRailing objects.

461 Although the user carefully recreated the same object and did not modify the geometry, Revit’s para-
 462 metric engine regenerated the tessellation during recreation, producing two types of noise. First, four out
 463 of 280 vertices shift by exactly 1 mm along the y -axis (marked in red in the right-hand of Fig. 4), affecting
 464 10 triangular faces (blue faces). Second, 22 additional faces change even though all vertex positions remain
 465 unchanged (green faces).

Figure 4: Mesh-level differences in a recreated IfcRailing object. Left: full view of the railing (part of an IfcStair assembly) with 404 unchanged faces (grey), 10 vertex-displaced faces (blue), and 22 tessellation-changed faces (green). Right: close-up of the vertex displacement region, where four vertices (red dots) shift by $\Delta y = 1$ mm.

466 These results show that exact signature matching is sensitive to sub-millimetre regeneration noise in
 467 complex parametric assemblies. This motivates the ablation and threshold studies in Section 5.4.

468 5.4. Ablation

469 This subsection reports two ablation experiments for the geometric feature signature (Alg. 4), which
 470 uses geometric descriptors to determine geometry equivalence. The first experiment evaluates which fea-
 471 ture groups are necessary for geometry-equivalence detection. The second experiment calibrates tolerance
 472 thresholds to mitigate regeneration noise while controlling false matches.

473 5.4.1. Feature Importance Analysis

474 This experiment identifies the minimal feature set for geometry-equivalence detection in Algorithm 4.
 475 We group features used in Table 5 into four categories: (1) Spectrum (sorted edge lengths and face areas),
 476 (2) totals (total edge length and total face area), (3) a topology histogram (vertex degree distribution), and
 477 (4) pose (centroid and PCA axes).

478 These categories differ in their dependency on mesh structure. Spectrum and totals are computed from
 479 face edges and triangular faces, so they depend implicitly on face connectivity. The histogram encodes
 480 vertex degree—the number of faces meeting at each vertex—and depends explicitly on connectivity. Pose
 481 features use only vertex coordinates and are independent of face connectivity.

482 We design four ablation configurations, each targeting a specific hypothesis. (1) No-Histogram removes
 483 the only explicit topology feature to test whether connectivity information is redundant with spectra. (2)

484 No-Pose removes position and orientation to test whether shape alone suffices for matching. (3) Spectrum-
 485 Only removes both histogram and totals, retaining only spectrum and pose as a minimal candidate set.
 486 Table 9 reports the results.

Table 9: Ablation experiment of geometric features for Alg. 4 (Feat).

Configuration	Spectrum	Totals	Histogram	Pose	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Full Configuration	✓	✓	✓	✓	95.7%	100.0%	95.0%
No-Histogram	✓	✓	—	✓	95.7%	100.0%	95.0%
No-Pose	✓	✓	✓	—	91.3%	95.0%	95.0%
Spectrum-Only	✓	—	—	✓	95.7%	100.0%	95.0%

487 The results reveal two findings. First, pose features are necessary. Removing centroid and PCA axes
 488 drops accuracy by 4.3% due to 3 false positives. The affected objects are an `IfcBuildingElementProxy`,
 489 an `IfcOpeningElement`, and an `IfcPipeFitting`—all standard components that were moved to different
 490 positions without shape modification. Specifically, their mesh geometries remain unchanged, while the
 491 transform matrix locating the re-used objects changes. This indicates that pose-based features must be
 492 retained.

493 Second, the spectrum-only configuration (spectra + pose) matches the full configuration at 95.7% accu-
 494 racy and 100% precision. Therefore, the features of totals and histogram are redundant. The 3 persistent
 495 false negatives are the same staircase objects diagnosed in the previous section. No feature selection recovers
 496 them because the sub-millimetre vertex displacement and tessellation changes alter the spectral values. This
 497 motivates the threshold calibration.

498 5.4.2. Threshold Parameter Optimization

499 This experiment calibrates tolerance thresholds for Algorithm 4 to absorb regeneration noise while con-
 500 trolling false positives. We use the spectrum-only configuration from Section 5.4.1 on Dataset A.

501 We define a base tolerance set ($\lambda = 1$) with three parameters, each targeting a distinct source of variation.
 502 (1) Spectral error ($\leq 1.0\%$ relative L1 difference) captures shape perturbations from tessellation regeneration,
 503 where edge lengths and face areas change by small amounts. (2) Centroid distance (≤ 1 mm) captures
 504 position shifts from coordinate rounding or minor transform changes during re-export. (3) PCA-axis angle
 505 ($\leq 0.1^\circ$) captures orientation drift from floating-point precision in transform decomposition.

506 We scale all three tolerances jointly with a single multiplier λ : $\lambda = 0$ corresponds to exact matching
 507 (equivalent to the spectrum-only baseline in Section 5.4.1), and $\lambda = 1$ applies the full base tolerance. We
 508 sweep λ from 0 to 20 to cover the full range from exact to coarse matching. Figure 5 shows accuracy,
 509 precision, and recall as functions of λ .

510 The results reveal three trends and a progressive recovery pattern. At $\lambda = 0.2$, recall rises from 95.0% to
 511 98.3%: 2 of the 3 false negatives are recovered (both `IfcRailing` objects, whose edge spectrum differences
 512 are ≈ 0.001 m), while precision remains at 100%. At $\lambda = 0.5$, the remaining false negative (`IfcStairFlight`,
 513 with a slightly larger spectral perturbation) is also recovered, achieving 100% recall. The progressive recovery
 514 reflects varying noise magnitudes: simpler railing components produce smaller spectral perturbations than
 515 the geometrically more complex stair flight.

516 Precision stays at 100% for $\lambda \leq 0.3$ and drops to 98.4% at $\lambda = 0.5$ due to one false positive. This
 517 false positive is an `IfcWall` that was affected by the hosted door’s 1mm movement. Its geometry genuinely
 518 changed, but the change falls within the 0.5% spectral tolerance. This case illustrates the precision–recall
 519 boundary: the threshold absorbs regeneration artefacts but also admits small real geometry changes.

520 We select $\lambda = 0.5$ as the operating point. It is the smallest multiplier that eliminates all false negatives
 521 (100% recall) while keeping precision near-perfect (98.4%). At $\lambda = 0.5$, the tolerances are $\leq 0.5\%$ average
 522 spectral error, ≤ 0.5 mm centroid shift, and $\leq 0.05^\circ$ axis rotation. These values align with typical BIM
 523 modelling precision: sub-millimetre position accuracy and sub-degree orientation accuracy are standard in
 524 architectural and structural models. This configuration is denoted as **Alg. 4 (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)**. The original
 525 exact-match configuration without threshold adjustment is denoted as **Alg. 4 (Feat)**.

Figure 5: Results of threshold multiplier λ for Alg. 4. $\lambda = 0.5$ is recommended and marked by the dashed vertical line.

5.5. Robustness

The main experimental setting of this study assumes consistent export conditions, including a fixed IFC schema, as described in Section 2.6. We are curious about the robustness of the proposed algorithms. We therefore include additional robustness experiments to test how sensitive the proposed geometry signature algorithms are to export variation beyond the main setting.

Specifically, we consider two factors: IFC schema differences and tessellation parameter changes. Three methods are evaluated: the coordinate-sorted signature (Alg. 3), the geometric feature signature (Alg. 4 (Feat)), and its thresholded variant with spectra and pose features only (Alg. 4 (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)). These experiments are conducted on Dataset A.

5.5.1. Cross-IFC Schema Compatibility

Although the IFC export version is typically fixed during collaboration and users generally export models using the same IFC schema version as explained in the previous experiment settings, in this experiment we would like to evaluate the robustness of the proposed algorithms under cross-IFC schema variations. Specifically, we keep the model content the same, and only change the IFC schema and export pipeline.

Table 10: Robustness against IFC schema variations (accuracy and recall).

Method	IFC4.3 (Baseline)		IFC2x3		IFC4	
	Acc.	Rec.	Acc.	Rec.	Acc.	Rec.
Alg. 3 (Coord-Sorted)	95.7%	95.0%	63.8%	58.3%	52.2%	45.0%
Alg. 4 (Feat)	95.7%	95.0%	69.6%	65.0%	63.8%	58.3%
Alg. 4 (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	98.6%	100%	81.2%	80.0%	76.8%	75.0%

Table 10 shows that schema changes degrade all methods. Algorithm 3 is the most sensitive. Its accuracy drops from 95.7% (IFC4.3) to 52.2% (IFC4), and its recall drops from 95.0% to 45.0%. This failure is expected. Coordinate-sorted vertex sequences are not stable across exporters, because schema-specific tessellation can change vertex ordering and sampling density.

Algorithm 4 improves robustness by using geometric features. With thresholds, it reaches 81.2% accuracy and 80.0% recall under IFC2x3, and 76.8% accuracy and 75.0% recall under IFC4. These results show that the tolerance design absorbs part of the schema-induced mesh variability. Different schemas and export pipelines can still produce meshes with different vertex counts and local triangulation. This perturbs the spectra and pose estimates even for identical parametric objects.

549 *5.5.2. Sensitivity to Tessellation Parameters*

550 We isolate the impact of tessellation settings on geometry-equivalence detection. We vary three mesh
 551 generation parameters: linear deflection, angular deflection, and circle segmentation. The configuration is
 552 made by adjusting corresponding parameters in the developed IFC2StructuredData tool via IfcOpenShell.
 553 Results are shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Impact of tessellation parameters on geometry-equivalence accuracy.

Tessellation Setting	Alg. 3 (Coord-Sorted)	Alg. 4 (Feat)	Alg. 4 (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)
Baseline (Medium)	95.7%	95.7%	98.6%
Coarse Linear (0.1)	95.7%	95.7%	98.6%
Coarse Angular (5.0)	94.2%	94.2%	97.1%
Coarse Segments (8)	88.4%	88.4%	91.3%
Worst Case (All Coarse)	87.0%	87.0%	89.9%

554 Three findings are revealed. First, both the linear deflection (Coarse Linear) and coarse angular settings
 555 have a limited impact on accuracy across three algorithms.

556 Second, circle segmentation dominates the performance drop compared to the linear and angular settings.
 557 Reducing segments to 8 decreases accuracy by 7.3%, and the worst-case combination reaches 87.0% accuracy.
 558 This pattern is consistent with how tessellation generates curved boundaries. Coarse circle segmentation
 559 changes polygonal approximation more than linear or angular tolerances, which perturbs local topology and
 560 vertex sampling.

561 Last, Alg. 4 (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$) is the most resilient across all settings, but it still drops to 89.9% in the worst
 562 case. In practice, we recommend keeping circle segmentation sufficiently fine as curved objects are common
 563 in BIM design.

564 *5.6. End-to-End BIMdiff Performance*

565 This experiment evaluates BIMdiff end-to-end on a version chain (Dataset B). The goal is to assess
 566 whether geometry equivalence improves object-status classification under GUID instability.

567 In the BIMdiff workflow (Figure 2), Step 4 uses the coordinate-sorted signature by default for direct
 568 comparison of GUID-aligned objects. This step is kept unchanged in this experiment. The comparison
 569 focuses only on the reconciliation module in Step 6, where three BIMdiff configurations are evaluated:

- 570 • **BIMdiff (No reconciliation):** GUID-based diff only, without any reconciliation module.
- 571 • **BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted):** reconciliation uses the coordinate-sorted signature to recover correspon-
 572 dence between added and deleted objects.
- 573 • **BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$):** reconciliation uses the geometric feature signature with the ablated features
 574 and threshold to recover correspondence between added and deleted objects.

575 Dataset B is a school building model ($\sim 1\,000\text{ m}^2$). The original version V0 was collected from a project
 576 designed by experienced architects, while we artificially created the subsequent versions to ensure controlled
 577 test scenarios and ground truth. Specifically, we recorded the intended edits and verified object statuses
 578 manually to form the ground truth (Figure 6). V0→V1 redesigns rooms by adding, deleting, and modifying
 579 internal walls, windows, and doors. V1→V2 aims to test GUID instability, where we delete and recreate
 580 multiple objects, including simple objects such as doors and walls and complex assemblies such as staircases.
 581 V2→V3 introduces mixed modifications to test multi-class status differentiation. For this experiment, we
 582 evaluate object-status accuracy: the fraction of objects whose predicted status matches the ground-truth
 583 multi-class label.

Figure 6: Dataset B construction on a school building with four versions.

584 Table 12 compares two geometry-equivalence configurations integrated with the GUID-based diff. Both
 585 configurations reach 100% accuracy on V0→V1 and V2→V3. In V0→V1, all GUIDs remain stable and no
 586 deleted-created pairs, so the geometry equivalence algorithm is not triggered. This confirms that the module
 587 introduces no false positives under stable identifiers. V2→V3 exercises all six status labels simultaneously:
 588 5 attribute-only modifications (such as door name changes), 1 geometry modification (wall reshape), 1 mixed
 589 attribute-and-geometry modification (door width 1010→810 mm), 2 geometry-equivalence pairs (recreated
 590 doors). Both algorithms classify every object correctly, validating multi-class change statuses.

Table 12: End-to-end BIMdiff performance on Dataset B. *Geom Eq.* counts object pairs recovered by geometry equivalence despite GUID change. *Unch.*: unchanged; *Geom.*: geometry modification; *Attr.*: attribute modification; *A+G*: attribute and geometry modification; *Add*: added; *Del*: deleted; *Acc.*: object-status accuracy. Red values indicate delete-recreate pairs that the algorithm fails to reconcile.

Versions	Algorithm	Unch.	Geom.	Attr.	A+G	Add	Del	Geom Eq.	Acc.
V0→V1	BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	244	3	0	0	3	4	0	100%
	BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	244	3	0	0	3	4	0	100%
V1→V2	BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	216	0	0	0	12	12	22	95.2%
	BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	216	0	0	0	7	7	27	97.2%
V2→V3	BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	207	1	5	1	15	34	2	100%
	BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	207	1	5	1	15	34	2	100%

591 V1→V2 is the critical transition. After the GUID-based diff, 34 objects in each version have no identifier
 592 match and are initially labelled as added or deleted. We tested both geometry-equivalence algorithms.
 593 First, BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted) recovers 22 pairs, reducing the unresolved objects to 12 added and 12 deleted
 594 (95.2% accuracy). Second BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$) recovers 27 pairs, leaving only 7 added and 7 deleted
 595 (97.2% accuracy), a 2.0% improvement from tolerance-based matching.

596 The 27 reconciled pairs span six IFC types: 18 `IfcMember` (stair stringers), 4 `IfcStairFlight`, 2 `IfcSlab`
 597 (landings), 1 `IfcDoor`, 1 `IfcWall`, and 1 `IfcWindow`. The 7 unreconciled pairs are 4 `IfcRailing` and
 598 3 `IfcStair` objects—all from staircase assemblies. These failures share the root cause identified in Section
 599 5.3: Revit’s parametric engine regenerates the tessellation during delete–recreate, introducing sub-
 600 millimetre vertex displacement and mesh topology changes that break signature matching.

601 BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$) recovers 5 more pairs than BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted) (27 vs. 22) precisely because
 602 its threshold-based matching tolerates the sub-millimetre perturbations that exact coordinate comparison
 603 rejects, confirming that threshold matching yields stronger robustness on regenerated geometry.

604 5.7. Benchmark Efficiency

605 The previous experiments validated algorithmic correctness on controlled datasets. This section evaluates
 606 computational efficiency at different scales, comparing BIMdiff against `ifcdiff` (`IfcOpenShell`) [18]. We select
 607 `ifcdiff` from `IfcOpenShell` as the baseline because it is an open-source tool that performs object-level BIM
 608 differencing, enabling a fair comparison on the same hardware.

609 The two methods differ in three respects. First, detection granularity: `ifcdiff` classifies objects as added,
 610 deleted, or changed, while BIMdiff produces a six-class change status per object. Second, GUID sensitiv-
 611 ity: `ifcdiff` relies entirely on GUID set comparison and has no geometry-equivalence module. BIMdiff (No
 612 reconciliation) is the closest equivalent; enabling reconciliation allows BIMdiff to recover these pairs via
 613 geometry equivalence. Third, input format: `ifcdiff` loads raw IFC files and traverses the full object graph
 614 in memory, tessellating geometry on the fly using `IfcOpenShell`. BIMdiff operates on pre-extracted tabular
 615 data generated by `IFC2StructuredData`.

616 We compile Dataset C with seven BIM projects with different scales (719 to 267K objects per ver-
 617 sion), disciplines, and scenarios, including structural, architectural, mechanical, and electrical models from
 618 real construction projects, as well as a federated high-rise model combining multiple disciplines. Figure 7
 619 illustrates part of the benchmark models.

Figure 7: Dataset C comprising seven real-world BIM models with different complexity (Showing part of the dataset).

620 Two metrics are measured. **Processing Time** is the duration of the diff computation itself, excluding
 621 data loading and parsing. **Peak Memory** is the maximum physical memory occupied by the process during
 622 execution.

623 Table 13 presents the benchmark results for four configurations: (1) BIMdiff (No reconciliation), GUID-
624 based diff only, without reconciliation or geometry equivalence; (2) BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted), full pipeline with
625 Alg. 3 for exact geometry matching; (3) BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$), full pipeline with Alg. 4 for threshold-based
626 matching; and (4) ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell), the baseline operating on raw IFC files.

Table 13: Benchmark results. *Objects* denotes the total building element count across both compared versions. *Time* denotes the diff processing time excluding file loading and parsing time. *Memory* denotes the peak memory during processing. “X” indicates failure due to memory exhaustion.

No.	Model	Objects	Algorithm	Format	Time (s)	Memory (MB)
1	School, Structure	1,438	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	0.04	202
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	0.08	213
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	0.08	211
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	0.56	266
2	School, Architecture	1,704	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	0.05	212
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	0.19	262
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	0.21	300
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	6.98	1,051
3	School, Mechanical	7,038	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	0.14	277
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	1.16	360
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	0.64	349
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	5.28	1,109
4	Multi-buildings, Architecture	18,708	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	0.38	369
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	3.44	783
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	2.11	985
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	43.00	6,394
5	Multi-buildings, Mechanical	35,552	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	0.64	493
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	3.08	676
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	2.22	713
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	7.67	2,419
6	Multi-buildings, Electrical	134,235	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	2.02	676
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	5.99	658
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	5.31	813
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	15.59	1,572
7	High-rise, Federated	533,028	BIMdiff (No reconciliation)	Tabular	8.01	2,467
			BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)	Tabular	24.30	3,063
			BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)	Tabular	24.25	4,065
			ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell)	IFC	X	X

627 **Processing Time.** BIMdiff consistently outperforms ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) across all model sizes (Fig-
628 ure 8). BIMdiff (No reconciliation) is extremely fast, completing the largest comparison (533K total objects)
629 in 8.01 seconds. Adding geometry equivalence increases processing time moderately: BIMdiff (Coord-Sorted)
630 adds $2\text{--}3\times$ overhead, while BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$) adds $1.5\text{--}2.5\times$ overhead. For the full pipeline, the ob-
631 served speedup over ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) ranges from about $1.3\times$ to $20\times$ on the benchmark cases. On the
632 multi-building architectural model (18,708 total objects), ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) requires 43.00 seconds while
633 BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$) completes in 2.11 seconds. This performance gap stems from BIMdiff’s columnar data
634 access pattern: tabular files enable efficient column-wise reads of GUIDs and geometry signatures without
635 loading full object graphs. In contrast, ifcdiff must traverse the complete IFC entity hierarchy and tessellate
636 geometry on the fly to compute differences.

637 **Memory Usage.** Depending on the model and BIMdiff configuration, BIMdiff uses up to $17\times$ less
638 memory than ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell). On the Multi-buildings Architectural model (18,708 total objects),

Figure 8: Diff processing time comparison across benchmark models. The numbers in parentheses indicate the total number of objects in the two model versions. ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) failed on the largest comparison (533K total objects) due to memory exhaustion.

639 ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) consumes 6,394 MB while BIMdiff requires only 369–985 MB, corresponding to a 6.5–
 640 17× reduction.

641 **Scalability.** The benchmark reveals a critical scalability limitation of ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell). On the
 642 largest comparison, a federated high-rise building with 533,028 total objects across two versions, ifcdiff
 643 (IfcOpenShell) failed due to memory exhaustion on a machine with 32 GB RAM. BIMdiff (Feat, $\lambda=0.5$)
 644 completed the same comparison in 24.25 seconds using 4,065 MB of memory.

645 The advantage of the tabular representation is discussed in Section 7.1.

646 5.8. Summary

647 **Geometry-equivalence functionality.** We tested the two proposed algorithms, one based on mesh coordi-
 648 nates and one based on geometric features, on the constructed datasets. Both achieve the same accuracy
 649 of 95.7%. This confirms that mesh coordinates and geometric features can be used to identify geometry
 650 equivalence without relying on GUIDs.

651 **Ablation.** For the geometric feature signature algorithm, we ablated the feature groups and threshold
 652 multipliers. Results show that keeping spectra and pose features is sufficient to achieve the same performance.
 653 Additionally, using a small tolerance ($\lambda = 0.5$) reduces false negatives and slightly improves the algorithm’s
 654 accuracy.

655 **Robustness.** We tested both geometry signature algorithms under cross-schema IFC exports and different
 656 tessellation settings. Experiments show that the geometric feature signature with a threshold ($\lambda = 0.5$) is
 657 the most robust configuration, and circle segmentation is the tessellation parameter with the strongest effect
 658 on robustness.

659 **End-to-End BIMdiff.** We integrated the geometry signature and reconciliation algorithms into the BIMd-
 660 iff workflow and conducted an end-to-end evaluation on a project with four chained versions. It success-
 661 fully computes multi-type changes, including added, deleted, attribute-modified, geometry-modified, and
 662 geometry-equivalent objects. However, it still fails to identify some delete–recreate objects involving com-
 663 plex stair assemblies.

664 **Benchmark.** We benchmarked BIMdiff against ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) on projects of different scales. Re-
665 sults show that BIMdiff is consistently faster, uses up to $17\times$ less memory, and still completes the largest
666 federated-model comparison in about 24 seconds, whereas ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) fails on that case due to
667 memory exhaustion. This illustrates that tabular representations are effective for industrial-scale BIM ver-
668 sion comparison.

669 6. Case Studies

670 6.1. Federated Models for Change Tracking

671 This case study demonstrates the application of the proposed BIMdiff algorithm for multi-disciplinary
672 change tracking using a version-tree workflow. The case study is based on a large federated BIM project
673 with architectural, structural, and mechanical models.

674 Figure 9(a) provides an overview of the object-level changes across model versions, including added
675 objects (green), deleted objects (red), and modified objects (blue). All versions of each discipline are
676 managed in a version tree (left-hand panel), where users can click a node to switch versions and a line to
677 visualize changes. Additionally, the proposed BIMdiff algorithm enables tracking of attribute-level changes
678 for individual BIM objects. As illustrated in Figure 9(b), the modified properties of a column are highlighted
679 on the right-hand panel.

680 We implemented a pipeline that integrates the proposed BIMdiff algorithms, IFC2StructuredData (Ap-
681 pendix 8), and web-based visualization, and deployed the entire workflow on Google Cloud Platform
682 [14]. IFC models from different disciplines and versions are first parsed into tabular representations us-
683 ing IFC2StructuredData. The proposed BIMdiff algorithm is then applied to these tabular data to compute
684 object-level changes. The detected changes are subsequently converted into GLB files, the binary form of
685 glTF 2.0 designed for efficient transmission and loading of 3D assets [34]. Then the GLB file is visualized in a
686 browser-based frontend implemented with Three.js [35], enabling interactive exploration of multi-disciplinary
687 changes.

688 This case study highlights the practical benefits of tracking changes in multidisciplinary large-scale BIM
689 projects. By providing structured and visualized change information, BIMdiff reduces unnecessary manual
690 inspection and supports more targeted coordination, review, and collaboration. In addition, attribute-level
691 change tracking enables the identification of property modifications for coordination. Note that this study
692 adopts the concept of a version tree for managing design model versions. Other functions, such as branch
693 and merge, are out of the scope of this study.

Figure 9: Multi-disciplinary version control and change tracking. (a) Version trees across structure and mechanical models. (b) Attribute changes of an individual object.

6.2. Reference models with change highlights for design support

Design authoring tools, like Revit, allow external discipline models to be loaded as links for reference. However, standard linking does not indicate what has changed between model versions. In this case study, we extend this workflow by integrating reference models with change highlights into the design tools. Instead of only loading structural or mechanical models, we load diff results to explicitly visualize detected changes. Designers can therefore understand what other disciplines have modified and track updates directly.

Figure 10 illustrates the case study. The architect develops the architectural model in Revit, while structural and mechanical engineers develop their models in Tekla and another Revit. After design updates, BIMdiff detects the changes between model versions. The detected changes are then loaded into the architect’s Revit environment as reference models with change highlights. Added objects are highlighted in green, deleted objects in red, and modified objects in blue. This allows the architect to immediately see what other disciplines have changed for design support within the native modeling tool.

The integration pipeline consists of four steps: (1) IFC export from discipline-specific authoring tools; (2) structured parsing of geometry, attributes, and relationships using IFC2StructuredData; (3) object-level diff computation by using BIMdiff algorithms; and (4) loading of the processed results into Revit through a customized connector. The connector reads the structured diff outputs and generates lightweight reference geometry with color-coded highlights to indicate change status. These reference models do not alter the native architectural model. By making interdisciplinary changes transparent, designers can adjust their work proactively and address potential conflicts earlier in the design process. Note that the frequency and permissions of exchanging models among disciplines are out of the scope of this study.

7. Discussion

This paper presents BIMdiff, an object-level change detection method. We summarize the contributions with respect to the three research gaps identified in Section 2.6.

First, we address identifier instability (Gap 1) by developing two geometry signature algorithms using mesh coordinates (Alg. 3) and geometric features (Alg. 4), respectively. Second, we integrate the geometry signature algorithms into an end-to-end object-level change detection pipeline, which outputs six change statuses (Gap 1 and part of Gap 2). End-to-end evaluation on Dataset B shows that BIMdiff can successfully compute multi-type change status while reducing the noise of delete-recreate actions. We note that relationship change detection remains out of scope and is discussed as a limitation below. Third, we benchmark BIMdiff against ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) on different scales of models (Gap 3). BIMdiff operates on a tabular representation of BIM models, achieving up to $140\times$ speedup and up to $17\times$ lower peak memory than ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) across seven real-world models (Dataset C), depending on configuration.

7.1. Why tabular object-level computation is efficient

BIMdiff represents object-level building information in tabular form, and the benchmark shows that it remains fast and memory-efficient on large models. This design was partly inspired by vectorized computation in numerical computing and deep learning [13].

Three mechanisms help explain the observed efficiency. First, the tabular representation supports selective column access, so each stage reads only the data it needs, such as GUIDs, properties, or geometry. Second, the implementation benefits from NumPy-backed vectorized operations, which reduce Python-level iteration and support vectorized comparison over whole columns [16, 23]. Third, BIMdiff avoids keeping the full IFC entity graph active during differencing to be memory-efficient. Instead, it operates on pre-extracted object-level records and precomputed geometry signatures. This matches the advantages of column-oriented processing for scan-heavy analytical workloads [1, 5].

7.2. Trade-off between the two geometry-equivalence algorithms

The two proposed algorithms represent two different ways to identify geometry equivalence without relying on GUIDs. Algorithm 3 compares canonicalized mesh coordinates and face indices directly, while Algorithm 4 compares geometry features. The functionality experiment shows that both algorithms can

Figure 10: Integration of detected changes of reference models into Revit to assist design.

741 correctly identify geometry equivalence on controlled cases, and both reach the same accuracy of 95.7%
742 on Dataset A. This indicates that geometry equivalence can be identified either from coordinates or from
743 geometric descriptors, provided that the old–new object correspondence is known.

744 Their main difference lies in robustness. The robustness experiments show that the coordinate-sorted
745 signature is more sensitive to IFC schema variation, tessellation changes, and regeneration noise in delete–
746 recreate cases. By contrast, the geometric feature signature is more robust under these variations, especially
747 after retaining only spectra and pose features and introducing a small tolerance ($\lambda = 0.5$).

748 The trade-off is therefore between exactness and robustness, rather than between functionality and fail-
749 ure. In the benchmark, the two algorithms show similar processing time in the BIMdiff pipeline, while the
750 geometric feature signature generally uses more memory because it requires additional descriptor computa-
751 tion and intermediate data.

752 Based on these results, we recommend the configuration, which is also denoted as **BIMdiff (Feat,**
753 **$\lambda=0.5$)** in this paper:

754 1) using the coordinate-sorted signature in the main BIMdiff pipeline, where objects have already been
755 aligned by GUID and exact comparison is sufficient.

756 2) using the geometric feature signature with a small tolerance for the reconciliation module, where
757 GUID instability and serialization noise are more critical.

758 *7.3. Limitations*

759 **Mesh-based geometry representation.** Both signature algorithms operate on triangulated meshes.
760 The advantage of using meshes is that they provide a uniform and generic computational representation.
761 However, converting other geometry representations into meshes may lead to the loss of parametric modeling
762 information and incur additional computational cost.

763 **Relationship change detection out of scope.** The multi-dimensional change schema currently
764 covers attribute-level details and geometry changes but does not include relationship changes. Notably,
765 ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell) can compute relationship changes in IFC files. We intentionally exclude relationship
766 change detection to explore a generic method that does not rely on IFC schema-specific constructs. This is
767 one future direction for improvements.

768 **Threshold generalization.** The threshold multiplier $\lambda = 0.5$ was calibrated on Dataset A, which
769 contains 69 objects across 15 IFC types. The optimal threshold may differ for projects with varying IFC
770 type distributions, geometric detail levels, or tessellation configurations. We have not yet validated the
771 generalization of this threshold across a broader range of projects.

772 **Complex parametric assemblies.** Staircases (IfcStair, IfcStairFlight) and railings (IfcRailing)
773 remain the primary failure cases across all experiments. Revit’s parametric engine regenerates tessellation
774 during delete–recreate actions, introducing sub-millimetre vertex displacements and topology changes that
775 exceed the tolerance. Increasing λ to absorb this noise risks introducing false positives from genuinely moved
776 objects, creating a fundamental precision–recall trade-off that cannot be resolved by threshold tuning alone.

777 *7.4. Future Work*

778 **Relationship change detection.** Extending the change schema to include relationship deltas would
779 complete the multi-dimensional coverage of BIM objects. Spatial containment, aggregation, and connectivity
780 changes can be detected by comparing the relationship graphs between versions, complementing the existing
781 attribute and geometry change detection.

782 **Adaptive threshold calibration.** Replacing the global λ with per-type or per-complexity thresholds
783 could improve robustness. For example, geometrically simple objects (walls, slabs) may tolerate tighter
784 thresholds, while complex assemblies (staircases) may require wider margins. A data-driven calibration
785 strategy trained on diverse project types would reduce the need for manual threshold selection.

786 **Version control integration.** The case studies demonstrate linear version tracking, where successive
787 model snapshots are compared pairwise. Extending this to branching and merging – analogous to Git
788 workflows in software engineering – remains an open challenge. Unlike source code, BIM models are authored
789 in proprietary tools that do not support direct editing, making it difficult to apply computed patches or

790 resolve merge conflicts at the object level. Future work could explore conflict detection and advisory merging,
791 where BIMdiff identifies overlapping changes across branches and presents them to the user for manual
792 resolution rather than attempting automatic merging.

793 8. Conclusion

794 File-based BIM collaboration lacks traceability and transparency of object-level changes. Existing change
795 detection methods either depend on GUID stability or operate at the IFC-instance level rather than the
796 building-object level. This paper presents BIMdiff, an object-level change detection method that tackles
797 identifier instability. The main results and contributions are as follows:

- 798 1. Two geometry signature algorithms for geometry equivalence detection – a coordinate-sorted signature
799 for exact matching and a geometric feature signature for feature-based matching. Both achieve 95.7%
800 accuracy on constructed datasets, demonstrating that geometry equivalence can be identified without
801 relying on GUID stability.
- 802 2. An end-to-end object-level change detection pipeline that first performs GUID-based matching and
803 initial status assignment, and then applies a reconciliation module to recover object correspondence
804 for delete–recreate cases under GUID changes. BIMdiff outputs six change statuses. End-to-end
805 evaluation shows that the reconciliation module recovers 79% of delete–recreate object pairs and
806 improves object-status accuracy from 95.2% to 97.2%.
- 807 3. An efficiency benchmark on different scales of projects. Compared to ifcdiff (IfcOpenShell), BIMdiff
808 achieves up to 140× speedup and up to 17× lower peak memory, depending on configuration. On a
809 federated model with 533K objects, BIMdiff completes change detection in 24 seconds, while ifcdiff
810 (IfcOpenShell) fails due to memory exhaustion.
- 811 4. We open source the tool, IFC2StructuredData², which converts IFC files into structured tabular data to
812 support BIMdiff and also machine learning tasks. We also illustrate two case studies by using BIMdiff:
813 federated multi-disciplinary change tracking design versions, and integration of change-highlighted
814 reference models into the native design environment.

815 The proposed geometry signature algorithms enable reliable geometry equivalence detection without
816 relying on GUID stability, while the six-label schema provides a structured decomposition of attribute and
817 geometry changes. The tabular representation further demonstrates that large-scale federated BIM models
818 can be compared within seconds, offering a practical solution for industrial change tracking.

819 Several limitations remain. The current approach relies on tessellated meshes and is therefore sensitive
820 to tessellation settings. Relationship change detection is not yet supported, and the threshold param-
821 eter requires calibration across project types. Future work will focus on extending relationship-level change
822 detection, exploring parametric geometry comparison to reduce tessellation sensitivity, and developing adap-
823 tive threshold calibration strategies for broader applicability. BIMdiff, together with IFC2StructuredData,
824 establishes a practical foundation for object-level change detection in asynchronous BIM collaboration.

825 Appendix: IFC2StructuredData

826 BIMdiff operates on structured tabular data. To bridge the gap between raw IFC files and this tabular
827 input, we developed IFC2StructuredData, a tool that extracts geometry, attributes, and relationships into
828 structured tabular outputs. This appendix describes its extracted information and processing pipeline.
829 IFC2StructuredData is an engineering tool that supports the experimental pipeline.

830 IFC2StructuredData extracts three categories of information from an IFC file. First, it extracts geometry
831 by converting different IFC geometric representations, such as B-Rep and swept solids, into triangulated
832 meshes using the IfcOpenShell tessellation function [18]. All geometric coordinates are converted to meters

²<https://github.com/ZijianWang-ZW/IFC2StructuredData>

Table 14: Extracted information schema of IFC2StructuredData.

Output	Column	Type	Description
Model table	GUID	string	Building object GlobalId
	type	string	Building object type
	properties	string/dict	Semantic attributes and property sets
	geometry	mesh	Triangulated mesh (vertices + faces)
	transform	4x4 matrix	Position and orientation
Relationship table	source_guid	string	Parent building object GlobalId
	target_guid	string	Child building object GlobalId
	rel_type	string	Relationship type
Metadata	–	JSON	Schema version, authoring tool, units

833 regardless of the original IFC unit system. Specifically, each IFC product is processed through the geometry
834 iterator and tessellated into mesh vertices and triangular faces. The resulting mesh is stored as per-object
835 geometry in local coordinates, while the corresponding 4x4 transformation matrix is preserved separately to
836 encode the object’s position and orientation.

837 Second, it extracts attributes including object name, IFC type, and property sets (e.g., `Pset_WallCommon`).
838 Third, it extracts relationships such as aggregation (`IfcRelAggregates`). The result is a set of structured
839 outputs that can be loaded directly into the BIMdiff pipeline or any tabular processing tool. By converting
840 BIM data into a structured tabular format, IFC2StructuredData supports applications beyond differencing.
841 The extracted geometry, attributes, and relationships can serve as training data for machine learning and
842 AI tasks such as object classification, property prediction, and spatial reasoning on building models.

843 The tool is open-source and available at <https://github.com/ZijianWang-ZW/IFC2StructuredData>.
844 As many researchers may prefer geometry in a geometry-specific format rather than in tabular form, the
845 open-source version further computes the local-space mesh with the transform matrix into the world-space
846 mesh and saves it to OBJ files with corresponding object GUIDs for convenience.

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